

Supporting Information

Low-Voltage Controlled Coercivity in Nanocrystalline Fe-Ni films by Magneto-ionic Effects

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S1: Control of the Fe-Ni alloy composition by adjusting the electrolyte composition

The composition of metal salts used in various electrolytes is detailed in **Table S1**. To achieve different Ni-Fe film compositions, the electrolyte was adjusted in such a way that the molar ratio of Fe^{2+} to Ni^{2+} is changed, while the total amount of Fe^{2+} and Ni^{2+} salts and the ratio of NiSO_4 to NiCl_2 is kept constant. Using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX, shown in **Figure S1**), the compositions were determined and reported as average values of Fe and Ni. These averages (listed in Table S1) were derived from multiple samples (illustrated in Figure S1) produced from each specific electrolyte setup.

Table S1. Concentration of Fe and Ni salts in $\text{mM}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ in the electrolyte solutions used to electrodeposit Fe-Ni films with different compositions. The alloy composition (in at.%) is given as mean average of the EDX results of different samples for each electrolyte with the standard deviation in brackets.

Electrolyte	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
$\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	422	412	404	384	360	339	308	270	219	142	0
$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	23	23	23	21	20	19	17	15	12	8	0
$\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	0	10	18	40	65	87	120	160	214	295	445
average composition	Ni	$\text{Fe}_{8.0}$ $\text{Ni}_{92.0}$ (1.2)	$\text{Fe}_{19.4}$ $\text{Ni}_{80.6}$ (1.9)	$\text{Fe}_{31.0}$ $\text{Ni}_{69.0}$ (4.0)	$\text{Fe}_{40.0}$ $\text{Ni}_{60.0}$ (3.0)	$\text{Fe}_{53.0}$ $\text{Ni}_{47.0}$ (5.0)	$\text{Fe}_{65.8}$ $\text{Ni}_{34.2}$ (2.6)	$\text{Fe}_{67.6}$ $\text{Ni}_{32.4}$ (1.5)	$\text{Fe}_{76.8}$ $\text{Ni}_{23.2}$ (0.9)	$\text{Fe}_{86.5}$ $\text{Ni}_{13.5}$ (2.7)	Fe

Figure S1. Relationship between Fe content in the Fe-Ni films, x_{Fe} , and the composition of the electrolyte solution, where $x_{\text{Fe}^{2+}}$ is the molar percentage of Fe^{2+} ions of the total amount of Fe^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions. The iron (e.g., the less noble metal) content in the deposit is higher than the iron content in the electrolyte, following the established anomalous co-deposition behavior of Fe-Ni alloy electrodeposition. [1–3] Blue data points are from energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) and the red data point is from energy electron loss spectroscopy (EELS) mapping (Figure 1e in the main manuscript).

S2: Examples for profilometry, atomic force microscopy and transmission electron microscopy

Profilometry and atomic force microscopy (AFM) are performed to extract the average thickness and root-mean-square (RMS) roughness values displayed in Figure 1a and b in the main manuscript, respectively. A representative profilometry line profile and AFM image of a Fe₅₃Ni₄₇ film (electrolyte 6 in Table S1) are shown in **Figure S2a** and **b**, respectively. For another sample from the same electrolyte solution, cross-sectional transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed, confirming the thickness and smooth morphology (**Figure S2c**).

Figure S2. Representative data for selected electrodeposited Fe-Ni films obtained from electrolyte 6 (see Table S1). a) Baseline corrected and smoothed profilometry line scan, b) AFM image and c) cross-sectional bright-field TEM image.

S3: X-ray diffraction diagrams of Fe-Ni films with different compositions

Figure S3 shows X-ray diffraction (XRD) diagrams obtained for representative films deposited from each electrolyte (see description in S1). In Fe-rich samples a single bcc Fe(110) peak is observed. Ni-rich samples exhibit two peaks corresponding to the fcc Ni(111) and (200) peaks, showing the polycrystalline nature of the samples. In the intermediate composition range, from 46 to 60 at.% Ni, very broad peaks indicate the presence of bcc and fcc nanosized grains with bcc and fcc phases, in agreement with previous work.^[4] From the peak positions, we calculated the lattice constants for bcc and fcc structures (displayed in Figure 1c in the main manuscript) via BRAGG's law.

Figure S3. XRD profiles for the compositional series of Fe-Ni films. XRD intensities are shifted vertically for better clarity. The average deposit composition as measured by EDX (see Table S1) is given on the curves. The vertical dotted lines mark the bulk BRAGG peaks corresponding to fcc Au(111) (ICSD-611628)^[5], bcc Fe(110) (ICSD-1953192)^[6], and fcc Ni(111) and Ni(200) (ICSD-646088)^[7], respectively.

S4: Microstructural and compositional analysis by high-resolution TEM, Fourier transformation of a TEM image, electron energy loss analysis, and EDX

Figure S4. Cross-sectional high-resolution TEM (HR-TEM), TEM-based electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) and SEM-based energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy. a) HR-TEM image and b) rotational average scan in the radial direction of the Fourier transform inset of a) a $\text{Fe}_{56}\text{Ni}_{44}$ film. This confirms the nanocrystalline microstructure and is in line with the presence of mixed bcc/fcc phases ($\text{Fe}_{60}\text{Ni}_{40}$ (bcc): ICSD-632932 and $\text{Fe}_{40}\text{Ni}_{60}$ (fcc): ICSD-632931). The peak at approximately 4 nm^{-1} is in line with a nickel iron ferrite ($\text{Fe}_{1.85}\text{Ni}_{1.25}\text{O}_4$: ICSD-84677). c) Measurements across the $\text{Fe}_{56}\text{Ni}_{44}$ film obtained from the EELS elemental mappings in Figure 1e) of the main text by averaging parallel to the film-gold interface, and d) EDX spectrum and elemental mapping measured on the film surface. Both, EELS and EDX reveal a uniform distribution of Fe and Ni in the film. Evaluation of the EELS mapping gives a composition of 58.7 at.% Fe, which is in good agreement with the composition obtained from EDX (56 at.% Fe) for this sample. The oxygen content measured by EELS cannot evaluate quantitatively the oxygen of the pristine film, because the TEM-lamella was exposed to air from all sides before the TEM measurements.

S5: Angle-dependent MOKE measurements and measurement of the virgin curve

Figure S5. a) Angle-dependent coercivity as extracted from angle-resolved in-plane MOKE measurements for Fe-Ni films with different compositions. The films exhibit an overall isotropic behavior in the film plane, a slight uniaxial anisotropy is only observed for the ultra-soft magnetic films with 67 and 82 at.% Ni. b) Hysteresis loop of an Fe-Ni film with 34 at.% of Ni including the virgin curve, which exhibits an initial low susceptibility indicative of domain wall pinning.

S6: Reversibility, (non)volatility, and speed of the magneto-ionic effect in Ni-Fe films

Figure S6. a) Reversibility of the magneto-ionic effect on coercivity in $\text{Fe}_{55}\text{Ni}_{45}$. This experiment was conducted on the same sample, 47 days after the initial reduction routine shown in Fig. 2b in the main manuscript. At the OCP state (1), the coercivity was measured at 5.3 mT, closely aligning with the initial value of 5.2 mT (see Fig. 2b). During the repeated, identical stepwise reduction routine, a very similar magneto-ionic response is observed, reaching a large MI effect of -95 % at (2). During subsequent voltage-switch off (3), the coercivity fully recovers. Thereafter, two additional reduction potential steps of -1.12 V and -1.14 $V_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ were applied until a stable coercivity state was reached, both achieving an -86 % MI effect. Again, the coercivity in the OCP state after each applied potential step fully recovers. Hysteresis loops corresponding to steps (1) to (5) are displayed on the right and confirm that also the shape of the hysteresis loop is recovered after the three reduction procedures. b) Investigation of reversibility and speed of the magneto-ionic effect. The sample was electrodeposited from electrolyte 6,

analogous to the sample in S6a. After a hysteresis measurement at OCP (1), a reduction potential of $-1.22 V_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ is applied and two hysteresis measurements (2) and (3) are performed. To reveal any time-dependency of the magneto-ionic effect, we plotted the coercivities of both hysteresis branches for this first potential step. For hysteresis (2), $|+H_c|$ ($|-H_c|$) is measured ca. 19 s (34 s) after the start of the potential step and both show an increase in coercivity compared to the OCP state, reaching $|-H_c| = 6.0 \text{ mT}$ at after 34 s. The measurement of hysteresis (3) starts 130 s after the start of the potential step and here the coercivity is decreased compared to the OCP state. Hysteresis (1) to (3) are depicted at the bottom left. The value of $|-H_c| = 2.8 \text{ mT}$ reached at (3) corresponds to a -50 % MI effect achieved within 152 s. The coercivity reduction might not be complete at this stage, but due to the strong hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), the voltage was switched off. The coercivity at OCP state was measured directly afterwards and did not show complete recovery even after 15 minutes (4). A second reduction potential of $-1.20 V_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ was subsequently applied, leading to a fast decrease of coercivity to 1.0 mT (5), corresponding to -83 % MI effect within 17 s. The corresponding hysteresis loop is shown on the bottom right. At this potential, HER was also strong, therefore, for further switching an even more positive potential of $-1.14 V_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ was chosen. For eight consecutive switching steps, a coercivity decrease at $-1.14 V_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ and subsequent coercivity increase at OCP is always observed. Towards the later cycles, H_c values at OCP drift towards smaller values, which points at increasingly non-volatile behavior.

S7: Enlarged anodic scan of the CV of Ni, Fe, and Fe-Ni films in 1 M KOH

Figure S7: a) Enlarged view of the anodic scan of the CV of Ni, Fe, and Fe-Ni films in 1 M KOH, displayed in Figure 3a in the main manuscript. A clear difference in the magnitude of the oxidation peaks for Ni, Fe and Fe₅₄Ni₄₆ films is seen. b) Current density j recorded during the stepwise application of reduction potentials in the in situ MOKE microscopy cell, exemplarily for the Fe₇₇Ni₂₃ film. Current spikes, which sometimes appeared as artefacts in the recorded current, were manually corrected. The transferred charge $|q|$ in Figure 3d in the main manuscript is obtained by integrating $|j|$ over time.

S8: MOKE microscopy images during magnetization reversal of the $\text{Fe}_{54}\text{Ni}_{46}$ film

Figure S8. MOKE microscopy images captured during the magnetization reversal of an $\text{Fe}_{54}\text{Ni}_{46}$ film in pristine state (top row) and under applied potentials in 1 M KOH solution: in high coercivity state at $-1.18 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ (second row), in transition state between high- and low-coercivity state at $-1.22 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ (third row) and in low-coercivity state at $-1.24 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ (bottom row). In the transition state, fine elongated domains, comparable to those observed in the pristine state, and large domains, as present in the low-coercivity state, are observed.

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